

STUDY THE PROFILE OF THE GRAPE GROWERS

Raut Vikram Keshavrao¹, Dr. Amit Kumar Mishra²,

1.Ph.D. Scholar, Bhagwant University, Ajmer

2. Assistant Professor, Bhagwant University, Ajmer, College of Agriculture, Department of Agriculture Extension and Communication (RJ)

vickyraut2137@gmail.com

(MS Received: 10.06.2023; MS Revised:21.07.2023; MS Accepted:22.07.2023)

MS 3081

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURE EXTENSION AND COMMUNICATION)

Abstract

The study was conducted with the specific objective of "Profile of the grape growers" in Nashik and Sangli districts of Maharashtra state considering the larger area and production of grape. The leading talukas of grape cultivation in Nashik districts were Niphad, Dindori, Satana & in Sangli were Tasgaon, Kavathe-Mahankal, and Palus. All six talukas were selected purposively. For the selection of grape growers, the purposive sampling method was used. Three villages from each talukas having maximum area under grape cultivation were selected for the study Ten grape growers from the list of farmers growing grape were randomly selected from each chosen village. Thus, a total of 180 grape growers were selected. For study, the variables taken namely as Age, Education, Farming Experience, Annual income, Family Size, Land holding, Social participation, and Extension contact. It is observed that more than 60 percent grape growers having middle age group, 50 percent studied up to Higher Education, followed by 58 percent of the grape growers had medium level of farming experience, Nearly half of the grape growers had medium level of annual income. Exactly 49 percent grape grower living in small size family, 42 percent of grape grower had small land holding followed by 48 percent having medium level of social participation and 41 percent with low level of extension contact.

Keywords: Grape, Profile, Maharashtra

Introduction:

Agriculture enterprise is the way of life in India. Agriculture sector is the backbone of the Indian economy. India is the second largest producer of fruit in the World after China. The major fruit growing states in India are Maharashtra, Tamilnadu, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Bihar and Uttar Pradesh. Grape (*Vitis Vinifera L.*) is a temperate fruit crop and also cultivated under tropical and subtropical regions in the world. It is originated in Asia Minor in the region between Black Sea and Caspian Sea which belongs to the family vitiaceae.

The grape is fairly good source of minerals like calcium, phosphorus, iron and vitamins like B1 and B2 also one of the most delicious, refreshing and nourishing fruit. Ripe grapes are easily digestible. Grape juice is a refreshing drink, a stimulant to kidneys and laxative. Ripe fruits are supposed to be the best table fruit. Wine making from grapes is a flourishing industry in many countries. Maharashtra, Karnataka, Punjab, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Haryan are the major grape growing states in India. Maharashtra is the leading grape producing state, where the total area under grape cultivation is 10,398 ha with annual production of 21.37 lakh million tons (2017). It stands very low as compared to other fruit crops. This is a challenging task for the scientists and the farmers.

Material and Methods:

Nashik and Sangli are the major grape producing districts in the Maharashtra. These two districts together accounted for more than 50.00% of area & production under grape in the state. Hence, based on highest area and production in the Maharashtra, the Nashik and Sangli districts were selected for study.

The primary unit of the sample was talukas of these two districts. The leading talukas of grape cultivation in Nashik districts were Niphad, Dindori, Satana & in Sangli were Tasgaon, Kavathe-Mahankal, and Palus. All six talukas were selected purposively. The secondary unit

of the sample was villages. Three villages from each talukas having maximum area under grape cultivation were selected for the study.

For the selection of grape growers, the purposive sampling method was used. Ten grape growers from the list of farmers growing grape were randomly selected from each chosen village. Thus, a total of 180 grape growers were selected and personal interviews with structured schedule was developed for the present study. Data were collected from primary sources to achieve the stated objectives. For this study, the independent variables taken namely Age, Education, Farming Experience, Annual income, Family Size, Land holding, Social participation and Extension contact.

Result and Discussion:

The results in Table 1 indicated that, more than 60percent grape growers having middle age group followed by Half of the respondents was having higher education, 28 percent of respondents having secondary education between fifth to tenth standard followed by 14 percent respondents having graduate level education. Fourty Five percent of grape growers were from medium family size and 49 percent grape growers were from small family size followed by 06 percent of big family size. Nearly 42 percent respondents was having small land holding capacity i.e. 1.1 to 2.0 ha followed 27 percent of respondents having semi medium land holding capacity. Exactly 58 percent grape growers were medium farming experience 17 percent having high farming experience followed by 25 percent grape growers were low farming experience. 49 percent of respondents were having medium annual income and 34 percent of respondents were high annual income followed by 17 percent of respondents were low annual income. Forty Eight percent grape growers were medium social participation followed by 27 percent grape growers were high social participation. Exactly Thirty One percent of respondents were medium extension contact and Forty One percent respondents were low extension contact.

Table 1: Profile wise distribution of Grape growers

Sr.No.	Category	Grape growers (n=180)	Percentage (%)
1	Age		
	Young	42	23
	Middle	108	60
	Old	30	17
2	Education		
	Illiterate	0	00
	Primary School (I to IV Std.)	15	08
	Secondary School (V to X th)	51	28
	Higher Secondary School (XI to XII th)	90	50
	Graduate (Above XII th)	24	14

3	Family Size		
	Small family	89	49
	Medium family	81	45
	Big family	10	6
4	Land Holding		
	Marginal (Up to 1.0 ha.)	30	17
	Small (1.1 to 2.0 ha.)	75	42
	Semi medium (2.1 to 4.0 ha.)	48	27
	Medium (4.1 to 10.0 ha.)	21	12
	Big (Above 10.01 ha.)	6	3
5	Farming experience		
	Low	45	25
	Medium	105	58
	High	30	17
6	Annual income		
	Low	30	17
	Medium	88	49
	High	62	34
7	Social Participation		
	Low	45	25
	Medium	86	48
	High	49	27
8	Extension contact		
	Low	74	41
	Medium	68	38
	High	38	21

Conclusion:

Hence it can be concluded from the study that more than 60 percent grape growers having middle age group, half of the respondents was having higher secondary education, 45 percent of grape growers were from medium family size, nearly 42 percent respondents was having small land holding capacity, exactly 58 percent grape growers were medium farming experience, 49 percent of respondents was having medium annual income, more than 48 percent grape growers were medium social participation and also medium extension contact.

References:

1. **Ahire, R.D., (1997).** A study on the adoption of improved management practices by the grape growers. M.Sc.(Agri.) Thesis, submitted to Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeet, Parbhani.
2. **Ankush, G.S. and Kolgane, B.T., (2008).** "Reasons for non-adoption of recommended Technology in grape cultivation" Research Review Committee Social Sciences subcommittee report the Department of Extension Education, Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani, submitted to Research Review Committee Social Sciences Sub-committee.

3. **Anonymous (2017).** Horticultural Statistics at a Glance 2017.
4. **Atar R.S, (2012).** Knowledge and adoption of recommended grape cultivation practices by the grape growers. M.Sc.(Agri.) Thesis, submitted to Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeet, Parbhani.
5. **Bhojar, S. D., R. D. Ahire and Kapse, P. S. 2020.** Study Profile of the Pomegranate Growers. *Int.J.Curr.Microbiol.App.Sci.* 9(12): 2006-2011.
6. **Chavan, S.S. (2005)** A study on adoption of recommended package of practices in grape cultivation by the growers in sangli district of maharashtra state M.Sc. (Agri.)Thesis, MPKV, Rahuri.
7. **Hinge, R. B. (2009).** "A study on diffusion and adoption of wine grape production technology in Maharashtra". *M.Sc. (Agri.), Thesis, (unpublished)*, University of Agricultural Sciences, Dharwad.
8. **Raut, P. N. (2006).** "Production constraints of orange cultivation in Nagpur district of Maharashtra", *Asian Journal of Extension Education*, 25 (1&2):1-4.